

Role of Ultrasonography in Evaluation of Focal Hepatic Lesions and its Correlation with FNAC

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Abstract:

Background: Hepatic lesions often necessitate precise characterization to guide appropriate clinical management. Ultrasonography aids in the localization and characterization of lesions, while FNAC provides cytopathological confirmation. This integrated approach enhances diagnostic accuracy, reduces the need for more invasive procedures like surgical biopsies, and facilitates timely intervention.

Materials and Methods: This prospective longitudinal study aimed at establishing the role of ultrasound in evaluating focal hepatic lesions and arrive at a final diagnosis by correlating the ultrasound findings with guided FNAC was conducted in the department of Radio diagnosis, Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College Kishanganj from 1st September 2022 to 30th April 2024.

Result: Out of total 50 cases, sonographic evaluation identified 12 cases (24%) as malignant (HCC and metas- tases combined), with FNAC confirming 10 cases (20%) as malignant. Sonographic findings identified 38 cases as benign (76%), while FNAC confirmed 40 cases as benign (80%). These results show a strong positive corre- lation between USG and FNAC findings.

Conclusion: Our findings demonstrate that USG serves as a reliable primary imaging modality for the detection and characterization of focal hepatic lesions. Additionally, the correlation between USG find- ings and FNAC results further validates the diagnostic accuracy of USG in identifying the hepatic lesions.

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Introduction

Focal liver lesions are routinely encountered in everyday practice of surgeons, radiologists etc. The diagnosis of various hepatic lesions is extremely crucial for their appropriate management. [1]

Ultrasonography (USG) plays a pivotal role in evaluating focal hepatic lesions due to its non-invasive nature, real-time imaging capabilities, and widespread availability. Hepatic lesions, which can be benign or malignant, often necessitate precise characterization to guide appropriate clinical management. [2]

Ultrasonography, with its advancements in technology, such as Doppler imaging and contrast enhancement, provides critical insights into the nature of these lesions. However, despite its utility, ultra- sonography sometimes requires complementary

diagnostic procedures for definitive characteriza- tions. [3]

Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is an ad- junctive technique employed when ultrasonograph- ic findings are indeterminate. FNAC involves ex- tracting cells from the hepatic lesion using a thin needle, typically guided by ultrasound, for cytolog- ical examination. This method offers a minimally invasive approach to obtaining a definitive diagno- sis, which is crucial for the appropriate treatment planning of hepatic lesions. [4]

The combination of ultrasonography and FNAC leverages the strengths of both modalities. Ultra- sonography aids in the localization and characteri- zation of lesions, while FNAC provides cytopatho- logical confirmation. This integrated approach en-

hances diagnostic accuracy, reduces the need for more invasive procedures like surgical biopsies, and facilitates timely intervention. In this context, the role of ultrasonography in evaluating focal hepatic lesions and its correlation with FNAC is of significant clinical importance. This integrated diagnostic strategy is essential for differentiating between benign and malignant lesions, determining the nature of indeterminate lesions, and guiding therapeutic decisions. This review aims to explore the utility of ultrasonography in assessing focal hepatic lesions and to examine how its findings correlate with FNAC results. [5]

Materials and Methods

A Prospective study was conducted in the department of Radiodiagnosis at MGM Medical College and LSK Hospital, Kishanganj (Bihar) from 1st September-2022 to 30th April -2024. The study was conducted on 50 patients referred for ultrasonography. They were clinically suspected of having focal hepatic lesions with associated complaints. It also included patients incidentally found to have focal hepatic lesions on ultrasonography done for other reasons from both inpatient and outpatient departments.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients with complaints such as vague upper abdominal pain, jaundice, fever, abdominal mass, or unexpected abnormal liver function tests with focal lesions in Liver measuring more than 1 cm in ultrasonography.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with bleeding diathesis.
2. Patients with end stage Liver disease.
3. Patients with severe jaundice.

Methodology: Written informed consent was obtained prior to participation in study. Demographic and clinical details were recorded for patients included in the present study. Patients were kept nil by mouth ideally for 6 h so that bowel gas is limited

before ultrasound examination. In some cases, clinical condition of patient demanded an ultrasound examination without prior preparation. Conventional gray scale sonography and color doppler study were performed with 2-5 MHZ frequency curvilinear transducer on real time in all planes. The lesions were identified, characterized and vascularity of the mass was assessed. The observations were noted in a pre-decided proforma. Those patients with sonological diagnosis such as of metastasis, abscess, hepatocellular carcinoma, hemangioma with atypical and suspicious features etc. were further evaluated by USG guided FNAC.

Laboratory investigations including complete blood count, bleeding time, clotting time, liver function test, prothrombin time, etc. were recorded and FNAC was performed after explaining the procedure to the patient and taking an informed written consent. Local area was cleaned with betadine and spirit. Local anesthesia was used in all the patients. The procedure was done using 20-22-gauge spinal needle. Patient was asked to take in and hold breath or to push out the anterior abdomen for better visualization of the hepatic lesion. Free hand technique under the guidance of USG was done and aspiration was achieved by multiple passages through the lesion. Four wet slides were prepared and sent for cytological evaluation in the preservative of absolute alcohol. Slides were processed and reported by department of pathology at MGM Medical College & LSK Hospital. After the procedure the patients were observed, and repeat USG was done to look for complications. No procedure related complications were observed in present study. All details, cytological and radiological opinions were entered in proforma and compared.

Ethical approval for our study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of MGM Medical College & LSK Hospital, located in Kishanganj, Bihar.

Result

Table 1: Age Distribution (n=50)

Age Group (years)	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
0-20	3	6%
21-40	15	30%
41-60	22	44%
61-80	10	20%
Total	50	100%
Mean Age	52.44±12.45	

Figure 1: Age Distribution

Most common age of presentation was observed to be 41 to 60 years.

Table 2: Sex Distribution (n=50)

Sex	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Male	28	56%
Female	22	44%
Total	50	100%

Table 2: Sex Distribution

There was a slight male predominance observed with 56% of the patients being male and 44% being female.

Table 3: Distribution of Symptoms (n=50)

Symptoms	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Abdominal pain	30	60%
Jaundice	10	20%
Weight loss	8	16%
Fever	6	12%
Asymptomatic	5	10%

Table 3: Distribution of Symptoms

The distribution of symptoms among patients with focal liver lesions reveals that the most common symptom is abdominal pain, reported by 60% of the patients. Jaundice is the second most prevalent symptom, affecting 20% of the patients. Weight loss is experienced by 16% of the patients, while fever is present in 12% of the cases. Notably, 10% of the patients are asymptomatic.

Table 4: Pro-forma for sonographic features observed in various Hepatic lesions

- 1.SIZE OF LESION
- 2.SHAPE OF THE LESION(well or ill defined)
- 3.NUMBER OF LESIONS(SINGLE OR MULTIPLE)
- 4.ECHOGENECITY
- 5.LOBE OF THE LIVER INVOLVED(Right, Left or both lobes).
- 6.VASCULARITY ON COLOR DOPPLER STUDY.
- 7.CALCIFICATION
- 8.NECROSIS
- 9.ASSOCIATED HEPATOMEGALY
- 10.ASSOCIATED PORTAL VEIN THROMBOSIS/ FEATURES OF PORTAL HYPERTENSION
- 11.BACKGROUND LIVER CIRROHIS

Table 5: Distribution of cases on the basis of echogenicity on ultrasound.

SONOGRAPHIC FEATURES.	SUBTYPE.	NUMBER OF CASES
<u>HYPERECHOIC</u>	HEMANGIOMAS	11
	FOCAL NODULAR HYPERPLASIA	10
	METASTASIS	1
<u>HYPOECHOIC</u>	HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA	5
	ABSCCESS	6
	LYMPHOMA	2
<u>ISOECHOIC</u>	REGENERATIVE NODULES	9
	METASTASES	1
<u>MIXED ECHOGENECITY</u>	METASTASES	3
	HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA	2

Table 6: Distribution of cases diagnosed by FNAC

CATEGORY	NUMBER OF CASES
HCC	5
METASTASES	5
HEMANGIOMAS.	11
FOCAL NODULAR HYPERPLASIA.	11
ABSCCESS.	6
REGENERATIVE NODULE.	9
LYMPHOMA.	3

The distribution of sonographic features among various hepatic lesion subtypes reveals that hyperechoic lesions are primarily represented by benign conditions.

Hemangiomas are the most common hyperechoic lesions, with 11 cases, followed closely by Focal

Nodular Hyperplasia (FNH), which accounts for 10 cases. Metastases are less frequent among hyperechoic lesions, with only 1 case.

Hypoechoic lesions display a broader spectrum of both benign and malignant conditions. Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC) is found in 5 cases, while abscesses are seen in 6 cases. Lymphoma, accounts for 2 cases.

Isoechoic lesions include regenerative nodules, which make up 9 cases, and metastases, which are observed in 1 case.

Mixed echogenicity lesions comprise metastases, present in 3 cases and Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC), found in 2 cases.

The FNAC evaluation of different hepatic lesions showed 5 cases as HCC, 5 cases as Metastases. Hemangiomas were found in 11 lesions. FNH was found in 11 cases. 6 cases were confirmed as Abscess, 9 cases as Regenerative nodules and Lymphoma consisted of 3 cases.

Table 7: Comparison of total malignant and benign lesions on USG and FNAC.

Category	Number of cases on USG	Percentage	Number of cases on FNAC	Percentage
Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC)	7	14%	5	10%
Metastases.	5	10%	5	10%
Total malignancy	12	24%	10	20%
Category	Number of cases on USG	Percentage	Number of cases on FNAC	Percentage
Hemangioma	11	22%	11	22%
Focal Nodular Hyperplasia	10	20%	11	22%
Abscess	6	12%	6	12%
Regenerative Nodule	9	18%	9	18%
Lymphoma	2	4%	3	6%
Total Benign	38	76%	40	80%
Grand Total	50	100%	50	100%

Out of total 50 cases sonographic evaluation identified 12 cases (24%) as malignant (HCC and metastases combined), with FNAC confirming 10 cases (20%) as malignant. Specifically, HCC was identified sonographically in 7 cases (14%) but confirmed in only 5 cases (10%) by FNAC. Conversely, metastases were consistently identified in both sonographic and FNAC findings, each accounting for 5 cases (10%).

Sonographic findings identified 38 cases as benign (76%), while FNAC confirmed 40 cases as benign (80%). Hemangiomas were accurately identified, with both sonographic and FNAC findings reporting 11 cases (22%). Focal Nodular Hyperplasia (FNH) was noted in 10 cases (20%) sonographically and slightly higher at 11 cases (22%) in FNAC findings. Abscesses were equally reported by both

methods, with 6 cases (12%). Regenerative nodules were identified in 9 cases (18%) sonographically and confirmed in 9 cases (18%) by FNAC. Lymphomas presented a slight variation, with sonographic findings identifying 2 cases (4%) and FNAC confirming 3 cases (6%) as Lymphoma.

In our study, USG showed 12 cases to be malignant (24%), with 7 cases as HCC and 5 cases as Metastasis. FNAC evaluation showed 10 lesions to be malignant (20%), with 5 cases as HCC and 5 cases as Metastases. Thus, USG has a positive predictive value of 83.3% for malignant lesions in our study. 38 cases (76%) were found to be benign sonographically, while FNAC showed 40 cases to be benign (80%). These results show a strong positive correlation between USG and FNAC findings.

USG image showing Hepatocellular carcinoma

FNAC image showing Hepatocellular carcinoma

USG image showing Liver Metastases.

FNAC image showing Liver Metastases.

Discussion

This study comprises correlation of ultrasonography and fine needle aspiration cytology in diagnosis of hepatic space occupying lesions.

FNAC was taken as the gold standard in comparing and correlating the diagnosis made by ultrasonography. For the diagnostic assessment of hepatic space occupying lesions, ultrasonography is a simple, affordable, rapid, safe, non-invasive procedure. During the study period, ultrasonography was performed on 50 cases of hepatic space occupying lesions. The various focal hepatic lesions encountered in the study were hepatocellular carcinoma, metastasis, hemangiomas with atypical and suspicious features, liver abscesses, FNH, regenerative nodules, Lymphomas etc. [6]

FNAC diagnosis of these 50 cases were considered for USG and FNAC correlation in our study. The number of male and female patients in our study was 56% and 44% respectively, with a male: female ratio of 1.27: 1. The age of the patients ranged from 18- 60 years with a mean age of 52.44 years. In our study most hepatic lesions were found in the 41-60 years age group. In the present study, symptoms among patients with focal liver lesions reveals that the most common symptom is abdominal pain, reported by 60% of the patients. Jaundice is the second most prevalent symptom, affecting 20% of

the patients. Weight loss is experienced by 16% of the patients, while fever is present in 12% of the cases. Notably, 10% of the patients are asymptomatic. In the present study, comparison of sonographic features reveals distinct characteristics for each lesion type. Hepatomegaly is commonly observed in cases of abscesses and tumours. Single lesions are more frequently found in benign lesions compared to malignant lesions. Conversely, multiple lesions are more prevalent in malignant lesions. Abscesses however can also occur as multiple lesions. In terms of lobar involvement, the right lobe is most commonly affected across all lesion types. The left lobe and both lobes are less commonly involved. Shape analysis indicates that most benign lesions predominantly present with a round shape and regular borders while abscesses and malignant lesions are more likely to have irregular shape and borders. [7]

Echogenicity features highlight that hyperechoic lesions are most commonly associated with hemangiomas and tumors while hypoechoic lesions are prevalent in abscesses. Cysts are primarily anechoic, distinguishing them from other lesion types. Mixed echogenicity is relatively rare, observed in tumors and abscesses. Necrosis is frequently seen in abscesses and malignant tumours. Calcification is more common in malignant lesions and occasionally present in abscesses. This summary high-

lights the distinct sonographic profiles of different focal hepatic lesions, aiding in their differentiation and diagnosis. In the present study, among various hepatic lesion subtypes reveals that hyperechoic lesions are primarily represented by benign conditions. [8]

Hemangiomas are the most common hyperechoic lesions, followed closely by Focal Nodular Hyperplasia (FNH). Metastases are less frequent among hyperechoic lesions. Hypoechoic lesions display a broader spectrum of both benign and malignant conditions. Isoechoic lesions include regenerative nodules, and metastases. Mixed echogenicity lesions comprise metastases and Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC). Vascularity on color doppler study is observed in most malignant lesions, while benign lesions show no vascularity on color doppler with exception of a few abscesses which showed peripheral vascularity.

In our study USG showed 12 cases to be malignant (24%), with 7 cases as HCC and 5 cases as Metastasis. FNAC evaluation showed 10 lesions to be malignant (20%), with 5 cases as HCC and 5 cases as Metastases. Thus USG has a positive predictive value of 83.3% for malignant lesions in our study. 38 cases (76%) were found to be benign sonographically, while FNAC showed 40 cases to be benign(80%).

These results collectively demonstrate the high reliability and effectiveness of USG and FNAC in diagnosing hepatic lesions within the studied population.

Conclusion

Our findings demonstrate that USG serves as a reliable imaging modality for the detection and characterization of focal hepatic lesions. Additionally, the correlation between USG findings and FNAC results further validates the diagnostic accuracy of USG in identifying hepatic lesions.

Furthermore, our study highlights the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration between radiologists and pathologists in the diagnosis and management of hepatic lesions. The integration of imaging modalities such as USG with confirmatory procedures like FNAC enhances the accuracy and reliability of diagnosis, leading to improved patient outcomes.

Our study contributes valuable evidence supporting the pivotal role of USG in the evaluation of focal hepatic lesions, emphasizing its significance in clinical practice for the timely and accurate diagnosis of liver pathologies.

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